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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Rational drug use during pregnancy is a crucial aspect of maternal and fetal healthcare. Due to physiological changes during pregnancy and the potential teratogenic effects of some medications, prescribing drugs in this period requires special attention. It is reported that 80–90% of pregnant women use at least one medication during pregnancy (Akpınar, 2021). However, inappropriate drug use may lead to fetal anomalies, spontaneous abortion, or long-term developmental disorders (Fidancı, 2024).

Main Discussion: This presentation discusses the principles of rational drug use, emphasizing the changes in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics during pregnancy. It also reviews historical and current drug risk classification systems, particularly the FDA's traditional A–X categorization and the newer Pregnancy and Lactation Labeling Rule (PLLR) implemented in 2015. The limitations of the older system and the advantages of PLLR in providing narrative, evidence-based risk summaries are highlighted (Pernia & DeMaagd, 2016). Furthermore, the presentation includes an overview of the safety profiles of commonly used medications in pregnancy, including antibiotics, analgesics, antiemetics, antihypertensives, and gastric medications. It underlines the importance of individualized risk-benefit assessment, particularly in the use of drugs like ondansetron, where the balance between efficacy and fetal safety is still debated.

Conclusion: In conclusion, rational drug prescribing in pregnancy must be guided by current, evidence-based information, considering both maternal and fetal outcomes. Healthcare professionals should be aware of updated drug labeling systems and prioritize patient counseling and informed decision-making in clinical practice.

KEYWORDS

Rational drug use, pregnancy, pharmacotherapy, teratogenicity, PLLR, FDA classification

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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